

PROMOTING 21ST CENTURY SKILLS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract:

This article provides English teachers' experiences through 21st century skills in English Language Teaching (ELT) for a pedagogical transformation. The study used qualitative approach and a case study design to investigate the experiences of English Language teachers in Ivory Coast, a West Africa francophone country. The study recommended that a pedagogical transformation requires a communicative approach and lifelong learning to provide opportunities to update teaching and learning strategies for an effective language skills acquisition by all the learners and education system stakeholders.

Key words: globalization, transformation of human activities, internationalization trends, digital revolution, multilingualism, transformative teaching.

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Recently studies have found that integrating 21st century skills in teaching and learning is a catalyst to personal and societal development, Paschal and Mkulu (2020) demonstrated that the development of a modern society is firstly influenced by the significant provision of quality education which has potential to create and develop skillful citizens to contribute to the national growth and development. In the world, many teaching challenges that negatively affect the English Language Teaching (ELT) effectiveness could be teaching approach, class size, technology integration, multilingualism, teaching resources, and opportunities of practices. Thus, the integration of the 21st century skills encounter some contextual challenges.

Through a constructivist perspective, this case study applies the semi directive interview to evaluate the integration of 21st pedagogical skills in ELT in the Ivorian context. Participants used in this study were teachers' educators from public schools, private schools, vocational and independent educative institutions to understand the ELT experience in various context. Findings revealed that 21st Century pedagogy is promoting in teachers practices and that results in positive learning engagement. Yet, many contextual challenges and issues affect the effectiveness of ELT.

Although there are many considerable factors that contribute to the development of a modern society, the language spoken by the people within the society has significant potential to foster growth and transformation of any society in this ever-changing world. In this developing world, English has become the language of internationalization in most human activities as medium of education and communication (Derakhshan & Shirmohammadli, 2015).

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In the past decades and more in the 21st century, English Language Teaching (ELT) has been significant in native and non-native countries following globalization, transformation of human activities and internationalization trends (Chehimi & Alameddine, 2022).

According to the STATISTA report (April 1st, 2022), there were around 1.5 billion people worldwide who spoke English either natively or as a second language, slightly more than the 1.1 billion Mandarin Chinese speakers at the time of survey. The increase number of English speakers globally has been influenced by the English countries such as United States of America, British, Canada, and Ireland which have played a vital role in providing appropriate educational support to non-English speakers as a way to strengthen international relationships, global citizenship and competitiveness (Paschal, 2022).

Some countries intent to integrate English language in their curriculum so that to prepare their citizens with the aim of keeping pace with the changes and competitiveness happening in this globalized world. With this regard, educators and educational planers have been innovating variety methods of teaching and integrating English language into their systems of education. Yet Jha (2019) argued that there is a variety of ELT approaches, methods, and techniques in this 21st century. Moreover, nowadays, digital revolution paves a vital development in the digital devices which facilitates ease access to quality educational resources, structured learning in accordance with multimedia and constructivist learning approaches. Multiple tools permit access to comprehensive content with on-demand availability and with no requirement for additional resource provision and organized body or association (Pureta, 2015; Mohammed & Kinyo, 2020). However, Febiana (2019) noted that results in many teachings contextual challenges regarding the pedagogy, class size, ICT integration, multilingualism, teaching resources, opportunities of practices etc. So, in this changing world, Toffler (2006) asserted that “the illiterate of the 21st century will not be those who cannot read and write, but those who cannot learn, unlearn, and relearn”. In other words, a transformative teaching including communicative approach and lifelong learning is required to empower individuals and ELT practitioners in their teaching context. This means that one should be continuous leaning as teacher educators or educative system stakeholders to apply the best practices in their classrooms.

English language has become an essential tool for communication in this globalized world. With its eminence as the lingua franca of academic, political, social and business, the need for English as an international language in education, social and business has become a high priority for communication around the global. Given the vital role played by the 21st century skills in enhancing effective impact and exposure to students in today’s world, it’s crucial for 21st century skills to be integrated as a transformative pedagogy (Paschal, 2022).

Although, some of the country in the world such as Nigeria, Tanzania and Ivory Coast, a West Africa francophone country have tried to improve communication through technology, educators and young people in Tanzania and Ivory Coast are still experience difficulties in their classrooms and communication in general (Gougou & Paschal, 2022). Among the challenges are large class size which affect the learners’ collaboration in the classroom. Some learners get intimidation to participate or

contribute their informed ideas due to the large classes (Paschal, Pacho, & Adewoyin, 2022).

Furthermore, according to the experience of different practitioners in public, private, vocational and independent education in Tanzania and Ivory Coast, as non-English native context, it's been noticed that most of the learners in general English language classrooms find it difficult to closely follow the teaching process due to the fact that the teachers of English language face a significant challenge in managing the class. With this reality, learners find themselves losing motivation to keep up with the instruction given by their teachers about the English lesson something contribute to students drop out from schools. Therefore, the traditional methods of teaching and learning in educational institutions need to be reshaped and revised to enhance the effective learning (Mahona & Pacho, 2022). Moreover, Jiang, Perkins, and Pena (2021), emphasize that traditional teaching pedagogies need to change by integrating 21st century teaching pedagogy which has proved to be a transformative teaching and learning approach. Hence, promoting 21st century skills in teaching and learning can inspire students to enjoy their classes. Educators will have an effective chance to teach and influence students during the teaching and learning process in learning institutions in Ivory Coast and other non-English native contexts like Tanzania.

The objective of this study was to describe and understand the experience of English language teachers using 21st century pedagogy to empower learners with English Language proficiency and provide a pedagogical transformation in their teaching context.

In this changing world, Toffler (2006) asserts that “the illiterate of the 21st century will not be those who cannot read and write, but those who cannot learn, unlearn, and relearn”. So, this research intended to provide new perspectives for a pedagogical transformation including the 21st century skills and lifelong learning in ELT according to the experience encountered by teacher educators in Public, Private, Vocational and Independent English teaching institutions in Ivory Coast. Explicitly, this research will benefit the education system stakeholders, community, students and future researchers.

Our study aimed to describe and understand the experience of English language teachers using 21st-century pedagogy to empower English learners' language proficiency and provide a pedagogical transformation in their teaching context through a qualitative case study in Ivory Coast. Findings revealed that 21st century skills are promoted in curricula and teaching methods thus some contextual challenges. So, a pedagogical transformation in ELT is a useful approach to enhance the education system stakeholders' skills for an effective appropriation of the 21st-century skills in the teaching practices to value learners' English language proficiency. As recommendation, we state that engaging professional development programs, lifelong learning and community of practices should provide lot of benefits to English teaching and support the transformation in pedagogy if it is a self-engagement through a personal action plan. Following many researches, we recommend English language teacher educators' engagement in a community of practice as another lever to support the pedagogical transformation.

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